

CHEMICAL FEEDING METHOD OF LEMON PLANT USING LEAF STOMATA

Saitkulov Foziljon Ergashevich¹
Farhodov Orifjon Adhamjon o'g'li²
Olishева Maftuna Qahramon qizi³
Saparboyeva Shirinoy Hamidjon qizi⁴
Azimova Umida Nosirjon qizi⁵

¹Tashkent State Agrarian University

²⁻³⁻⁴⁻⁵Student of Tashkent State Agrarian University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7332771>

Annotation: Studied nitrate through the membrane is the next experience. If KNO_3 and valinomycin are introduced into the medium where the liposome is placed - a ball bounded by a two-layer artificial membrane, then a potassium "hole" is formed and K^+ and NO_3^- ions enter the liposome, it quickly swells.

Key words: Chemical, nitrates, metabolites, nitrites, water, forming an ammonium ion NH_4^+ , hydroxide ion OH^- , higher and lower plants, occurs inside the cell, as a result.

INTRODUCTION

Green plants under the influence of sunlight in the process of photosynthesis from carbon dioxide, water and simple mineral salts synthesize organic substances, which in turn provide food for humans and animals. As a result of this process, all green vegetation in the daytime releases a large amount of oxygen that living organisms breathe. Therefore, life on Earth is conditioned by the work of higher and lower plants. The scale and significance of this process in nature can be judged from the following data: green plants annually form up to 400 million tons of organic substances in terms of glucose, of which 115 million tons are on land, bind up to 170 million tons of carbon dioxide and decompose during photolysis into plants 130 million tons of water with the release of 115 million tons of oxygen.

For the synthesis of organic substances, plants on a global scale use up to 2 million tons of nitrogen and 6 million tons of ash elements. The reserves of nitrogen in the atmosphere are 4 10¹⁵ tons, but they do not determine the provision of crops with nitrogen, since plants use this element from the soil, not the atmosphere.

The plant receives more than 95% of carbon dioxide through the leaves and can assimilate ash elements and nitrogen from aqueous solutions by foliar nutrition. However, the main amount of nitrogen, water and ash nutrients comes from the soil through the root system [1-4].

Water is consumed by the plant and used in the process of photolysis nutrition and is evaporated by the leaves in a much larger amount. For the formation of 1 kg of dry mass of the crop, 300-400 kg of water is evaporated. Under adverse conditions, water consumption increases by 1.5–2 times, while under optimal conditions, water consumption decreases by 15–20% [5–8].

Due to the relationship with weather and climate conditions, regulation and optimization of plant nutrition and metabolism is not always possible. The content of nutrients in the soil in a form available to plants also depends on these conditions. Mobilization or immobilization of individual nutrients in the soil is also determined by the activity and direction of chemical, physicochemical and microbiological processes, the biological properties of the plant itself, the dynamics of the absorption of individual cations and anions during the growing season.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Hydrogen ions are pumped out of the cell through a proton pump, which, pumping protons out of the cell, creates concentration and electrical gradients.

In this case, alkalization occurs inside the cell, as a result of which the carrier can transport back into the cell under the action of an electrochemical gradient, both protons back and other anions. This transfer mechanism is called a symport. The opposite process - pumping out the H + proton from the cell and delivering it inside the cell to maintain the electrical neutrality of an ion with the same charge, is called antiport. The terms symport and antiport are proposed by Mitchell.

The intake of nitrogen is much easier. The NH₄⁺ cation in the aquatic environment is in the equilibrium

The NH₃ molecule penetrates the cell a thousand times faster than other electrically neutral molecules, with the exception of water. When passing through the membrane, ammonia takes a hydrogen ion H + from water, forming an ammonium ion NH₄⁺ and a hydroxide ion OH⁻

Alkalinization of the cytoplasm occurs, which interferes with the pumping out of the proton and the operation of the proton pump, while at the same time alkalization contributes to the flow of phosphorus.

Figure-1

EXPERIMENTAL PART

Anions NO_3^- , CN^- , I^- , pass through the membrane 100-1000 times more difficult than K^+ and NH_4^+ . These anions in high concentrations can destroy the membrane structure and are called chaotropic.

The proof of the passage of nitrate through the membrane is the following experiment. If KNO_3 and valinomycin are introduced into the medium where the liposome is placed - a ball bounded by a two-layer artificial membrane, then a potassium "hole" is formed and K^+ and NO_3^- ions enter the liposome, it quickly swells. If KCl is used instead of KNO_3 , then the membrane is impermeable to Cl^- . A small amount of potassium will enter the liposome due to valinomycin and the process will stop as a result of the diffusion potential, the liposome will not swell.

Water molecules have the highest rate of passage through membranes.

Literature:

1. Textbook. V.G. Mineev, V.G. Sychev, G.P. Gamzikov and others; ed. V.G. Mineev. - M.: Publishing house VNIIA im. D.N. Pryanishnikova, 2017. - 854 p.
2. Yagodin B.A., Zhukov Yu.P., Kobzarenko V.I. Agrochemistry / Ed. B.A. Yagodina. — M.: Kolos, 2002. — 584 p.: ill.
3. F.E. Saitkulov, B.Zh. Elmuradov. Influence of the nature of the methylating agent and solvent on the directions of the methylation reaction of 2n (methyl-, -phenyl-, -p-nitrophenyl) quinazolin-4-ones.2022/7/30

4. F.E.Saitkulov, Zakhidov K.A., Samarov Z.U. 2-Methylquinazolin-4-thionni “yumshoq” va “kattiq” methyllash agent and bilan methyllash. SamDU ilmiy ahborotnomasi 2015-yil, 3-dream. Samarkand 109- bet.
5. F.E.Saitkulov, Zakhidov K.A., Samarov Z.U., Synthesis and study of the methylation reaction of quinazolin-4-thione. Uzbekiston republic and fanlar Academy and magazines. № 4, 2015 yil. C-54-56
- 6.F.E. Saitkulov, B. J. Elmuradov, N. Sh. Ropijonova. Methylation of quinazolin-4-one with "soft" and "hard" methylating agents. International Journal of Development and Public Policy | e-ISSN: 2792-3991 | www.openaccessjournals.eu | Volume: 1 Issue: 8
7. F.E.Saitkulov, B.Zh.Elmuradov, K.Giyasov, Methylation of 2-methylquinazolin-4-one with “soft” and “hard” methylating agents. Universum 2022 12-Oct.
8. F.E.Saitkulov, B.Zh.Elmuradov, UV spectral characteristics of quinazolin-4-one and -thiones. Innovative developments and research in education international scientific-online conference Canada 21.08.2022. pp-10-12
9. Saitkulov F. E. et al. 2, 3-Dimethylquinazolin-4 (3H)-one //Acta Crystallographica Section E: Structure Reports Online. – 2014. – T. 70. – №. 7. – C. o788-o788.
10. Saitkulov F. et al. TITRIMETRIC ANALYSIS OF CALCIUM CATION IN" MEGATON" VARIETY OF CABBAGE //International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 10. – C. 134-135.
11. Sapaev B. et al. Synthesis of 2-methylquinazoline-4-thione with the purpose of alkylation of 3-propyl 2-methylquinazoline-4-thione with alkylating agents //AIP Conference Proceedings. – AIP Publishing LLC, 2022. – T. 2432. – №. 1. – C. 020009.
12. Boymuratova G. O. et al. To Examine the Processes of Biochemical Action Of 6-Benzylaminopurine with Cobalt-II Nitrate Dihydrate on the “Morus Alba” Variety of Moraceae Plant //Eurasian Journal of Physics, Chemistry and Mathematics. – 2022. – T. 3. – C. 39-42.
13. Sapaev B. et al. Study of methylation reactions of 2-phenylquinazoline-4-tion with “soft” and “hard” methylation agents and determination of its biological activity //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2021. – T. 258. – C. 04023.

